

CHARACTERISTICS OF KEY ADAPTATION INDICATORS IN NEWBORNS OF WOMEN OF ADVANCED MATERNAL AGE

M.A. Gulyamova¹, F.F. Tursunbaeva², Sh.Kh. Khodzhimetova³, M. Temirova⁴

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute^{1,2,3,4}

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Abstract. Objective: To examine key adaptation indicators in newborns of advanced maternal age.

Materials and Methods: The study included 76 newborns with a gestational age of 29–42 weeks, divided into two groups: Group I consisted of 42 newborns born to mothers of advanced reproductive age. Group II included 34 newborns born to mothers of fertile age.

Results: It was established that the conditions observed in the assessment of newborns in the first hours of life, born to first-time mothers of advanced reproductive age, were more prone to pathological processes, which also persisted during the period of auto-stabilization of internal organs. Assessing the health condition and further development of these newborns enables neonatologists and pediatricians to provide timely and qualified assistance when necessary.

Keywords: newborn, advanced reproductive age, asphyxia.

In modern obstetrics worldwide, the issue of pregnancy in women aged 30 to 44 years, i.e., during the late reproductive period, is highly relevant. Women of advanced reproductive age (over 35 years) account for 42.2% of pregnancies. According to domestic and international literature, pregnancy at this age is considered a high-risk factor for maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. Such pregnancies are preemptively classified as "problematic." The topic of "late" pregnancies and childbirth is widely discussed in the literature. The condition of newborns is closely related to the reproductive health of the mother. In our opinion, studying the less explored aspects of "late" pregnancies could help reduce maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. There are only isolated data in the literature regarding the clinical assessment of newborns born to women of advanced reproductive age.

Most studies examining the impact of maternal age on the condition of newborns focus on multiparous women of older age groups. However, there is virtually no data on the condition of children born to first-time mothers of advanced reproductive age.

Objective: To examine key adaptation indicators in newborns of advanced maternal age

Materials and methods. The study examined 76 newborns with a gestational age of 29–42 weeks, divided into two groups: Group I consisted of 42 newborns born to mothers of advanced reproductive age. Group II included 34 newborns born to mothers of fertile age.

The research included an analysis of the obstetric history of the mothers, assessment of the newborns using the Apgar score, as well as clinical, laboratory, and instrumental examinations.

Results and Discussion. The majority of all examined newborns (Figure 1) were those with a gestational age of 38–42 weeks (67.2%).

The number of newborns with a gestational age of 33–37 weeks was 3.6 times lower (18.4%), and the smallest group was composed of newborns with a gestational age of 28–32 weeks (14.4%). Among the examined newborns, the majority in both groups had a birth weight of 2500–4500 grams (54.8% and 55.9%, respectively). Nearly five times fewer newborns had a birth weight

of 1000–1499 grams, while only a small percentage (5%) had a birth weight of less than 900 grams. The largest subgroup consisted of newborns from Groups I and II with a birth weight of 1500–2499 grams, predominantly preterm infants. The main contingent of preterm newborns, including those with low birth weight (1500–2499 grams), very low birth weight (1000–1499 grams), and extremely low birth weight (<900 grams), were born to first-time mothers of advanced reproductive age (Table 1).

Figure 1. Characteristics of newborns based on gestational age

Table 1.

Body weight at birth	Group I n=42						Group II n=34					
	Full-term n=26		Premature n=16		Total		Full-term n=25		Premature n=9		Total	
	abs	%	Abs	%	Abs	%	Abs	%	abs	%	Abs	%
4500-2500	22	84,6	1	6,3	23	54,8	18	72	1	11,1	19	55,9
2499-1500	4	15,3	6	37,5	10	23,8	7	28	4	44,4	11	32,4
1499-1000	-	-	5	31,2	5	11,9	-	-	4	44,4	4	11,8
< 900	-	-	4	25	4	9,5	-	-	-	-		

The analysis of clinical studies of newborns in the early neonatal period showed that among all the examined infants, 27.6% were born with signs of asphyxia, and 1.5 times fewer had cardiorespiratory distress syndrome (CRDS) (Figure 2). The average Apgar score at the 1st minute for newborns in Group I was 6.4 ± 0.25 , and at the 5th minute it was 7.1 ± 0.21 .

The comparative analysis of Apgar scores in the examined groups showed a statistically significant decrease ($P < 0.01$) in the Apgar scores at both the 1st and 5th minutes for newborns in Group I compared to those in Group II (Table 2).

The comparison between the groups revealed that the number of newborns born to women of advanced reproductive age with low Apgar scores (0-3 and 4-6 points) at the 1st minute was significantly higher (62.5%, 71.4% respectively) than those born to women of fertile age. The

causes of asphyxia in newborns of women older than 35 years included: preterm birth, eclampsia, threat of miscarriage, fetal placental insufficiency, premature placental abruption, and chronic viral infections.

Figure 2. Comparative analysis of the incidence of perinatal asphyxia in the study groups.

Table 2

The comparative analysis of Apgar scores in the examined groups.

Indicators	Group I n=42	Group II n=34	P
Apgar score, 1 minute, points	6,4 ± 0,25	7,1 ± 0,21	<0,01
Apgar score, 5 minute, points	7,8 ± 0,23	8,2 ± 0,18	<0,01

Severe respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) was more frequently observed ($P < 0.001$) in newborns from Group I, while mild cases were more common in Group II. However, no significant differences were found between the groups when assessing moderate respiratory distress. (Figure 3.)

Figure 3. Assessment of the degree of respiratory distress in the examined newborns using the Silverman score.

Oxygen deficiency and respiratory dysfunction impair the establishment of hemodynamics and microcirculation, significantly exacerbating the adaptation process to extrauterine life. In this regard, we studied the clinical picture of the condition of newborns during the first 24 hours of life (Table 3).

A detailed analysis revealed that newborns with extremely severe and moderate conditions were significantly more prevalent among the newborns of primiparous women of advanced reproductive age ($P < 0.001$; $P < 0.01$). Respiratory rate, heart activity, and skin color were the most sensitive indicators of the newborn's condition. In our study, acrocyanosis and generalized cyanosis predominated in Group I ($P < 0.01$), along with jaundice ($P < 0.001$). Jaundice was due to the presence of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (NRDS) and TORCH infections in 5 cases. Respiratory indicators were weakened in over one-third of the children ($P < 0.01$), with pronounced dyspnea ($P < 0.001$). A decrease in heart activity was observed: muffled heart sounds, bradycardia, and tachycardia ($P < 0.001$). Muscle tone changes were identified, with a predominance of hypotonia ($P < 0.01$).

Table 3

Clinical characteristics of newborns at birth from primiparous women of advanced reproductive age and women of favorable fertile age

Condition	Group I (n=42)		Group II (n=34)	
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%
General condition:				
Extremely severe	5	11,9**	2	5,8
Severe	8	19,0*	6	17,6
Moderate to severe	15	35,7*	9	26,5
Satisfactory	14	33,3	17	50,0
Skin condition:				
Pale pink	18	64	23	67,6
Cyanotic	12	36*	7	20,5
Gray with marbling	7	16,7*	2	5,8
Jaundiced	5	11,9*	2	5,8
Cyanosis:				
Perioral	22	43	26	76,4
Acrocyanosis	12	33*	6	17,4
Diffuse	8	24**	2	5,8
Breathing:				
Puerile	26	61,9	24	70,6
Weak	16	38,1*	10	29,4
Dyspnea:				
Severe	10	23,8*	5	14,7
Moderate	8	19,0	9	26,5
Chest retraction:				
Retraction of flexible parts of the chest	18	42,9	13	38,2
Respiratory distress (RD)	16	38,0**	8	23,5

Muscle tone:				
Preserved	12	62	23	61
Reduced	13	38,2	9	26,4
"Frog" position	5	11,9*	2	4,8
Heart tones:				
Rhythmic	33	78,5	29	85,2
Irregular	9	21,4*	5	14,7
Dull	12	28,6*	6	17,4
Clear	30	71,4	28	82,3
Bradycardia	5	11,9*	2	5,8
Tachycardia	9	21,4	3	9,3

*Note: The statistical significance of differences between the groups: *P <0.01, **P <0.001.*

Thus, the condition of newborns during the first hours of life, those who experienced asphyxia, and the associated changes in muscle tone, skin color, heart rhythm disturbances, and respiratory insufficiency are directly related to the post-hypoxic syndrome.

Among the examined newborns, oxygen dependence was observed in 38.0%, body temperature instability in 39.5%, and the need for incubator care in 45.0%. In Group I, resuscitation measures were performed in 18 cases (43%), and 48% of newborns were oxygen-dependent. Among the examined newborns, 29% required incubator care, and 38.0% had body temperature instability. In Group II, resuscitation measures were performed in 26.5% of newborns, all of whom were oxygen-dependent. Body temperature instability was observed in 41% of cases, and 26.5% of newborns were placed in the incubator (Table 4).

The comparative analysis of the examined groups showed that resuscitation measures were performed twice as often among the newborns in Group I (66.6%), and oxygen dependence was more prevalent, being 2.5 times higher (68.9%) compared to Group II. The number of children with body temperature instability was nearly the same in both groups. The majority of children were placed on the breast at 2 hours of life (28.9%), with a significantly larger number of newborns in Group I ($P < 0.01$). Meconium passage occurred in the first 12 hours of life for the majority of children (72.4%). However, meconium passage was significantly more frequent in newborns from Group I in the first 24 hours of life ($P < 0.01$), with a single case at 48 hours (2.3%).

Table 4

Characteristics of certain indicators of the adaptation period in the examined newborns

Indicators	Group I (n=42)		Group II (n=34)		Total (n=76)	
	Abs	%	Abs	%	Abs	%
Was resuscitation performed?	18	43**	9	26,5	27	35,5
Oxygen dependence	20	48*	9	26,5	29	38
Incubator care	12	29*	9	26,5	19	45
Body temperature instability	16	38	14	41	30	39,5

When placed on the breast: Immediately	7	16,7	15	44,1**	22	28,9
2nd hour of life	15	36*	9	26,5	24	31,6
2nd day of life	7	17	7	20,5	14	18
Meconium passage: 12 h	30	71	25	73,5	55	72,4
24h	11	27*	9	26	20	26,3
48h	1	2	-		1	4%

*Note: The statistical significance of differences between the groups: *P <0.01, **P <0.001.*

Studies have shown that most of the children born to mothers of advanced reproductive age underwent resuscitation measures, were oxygen-dependent, had more frequent temperature instability, and required incubator care.

Analyzing the conditions outlined above in the evaluation of newborns during the first hours of life, it is important to note that children born to older primiparous mothers were more prone to pathological processes, which reduced their adaptive abilities during the early cardiorespiratory adaptation period and the period of autostabilization of internal organs. Evaluating the health status of newborns and their further development, particularly those born to women of advanced reproductive age, will enable neonatologists and pediatricians to provide timely, qualified assistance when necessary.

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